

Ordinary Differential Equations- Shooting Method

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1 Introduction

Ordinary Differential Equations (ODEs) are fundamental mathematical tools used to describe processes that evolve over time, space or any relevant variable. They model a wide range of real-world phenomena, from population dynamics to mechanical vibrations. In many cases, ODEs can be viewed as simplified versions of Partial Differential Equations (PDEs), making them useful baseline models for understanding more complex systems.

ODE problems typically fall into two main categories: Initial Value Problems (IVPs) and Boundary Value Problems (BVPs). These two classes have distinct properties, which influence the methods used to solve them.

IVPs require all conditions to be specified at a single point. Under mild conditions (e.g., when the ODE is Lipschitz continuous), the existence and uniqueness theorem guarantees a unique solution. Analytical techniques such as separation of variables, integrating factors, and Laplace transforms are commonly applied to IVPs. Numerically, methods like the Runge–Kutta family (e.g., RK4) are widely used. However, for stiff IVPs—where the system exhibits widely varying timescales—explicit methods like RK4 become inefficient because they require extremely small step sizes to maintain stability. In such cases, implicit or multistep methods are preferred. Examples of IVPs include Newton’s law of cooling and the simple harmonic oscillator.

BVPs, in contrast, specify conditions at more than one point in the domain. While linear BVPs often have unique solutions, nonlinear BVPs may have none, one, or multiple solutions. The lack of guaranteed uniqueness makes them more challenging to analyse and solve numerically. Analytical methods often involve transforming a BVP into an IVP (e.g., through similarity solutions or ansatz methods) before applying known techniques. Numerically, BVPs are typically addressed using methods such as finite difference, finite element, or the shooting method. Classic examples include the Falkner–Skan equation in fluid dynamics and the beam bending equation in structural mechanics.

This project focuses on the shooting method, a numerical technique for solving BVPs in both one-dimensional and multi-dimensional settings. The shooting method transforms a BVP into an IVP by introducing an initial guess for the unknown initial conditions that would satisfy the boundary conditions. By integrating the ODE with this guessed setup, we obtain a solution that may or may not meet the boundary requirements. To refine the guess, we define a residual or error function that quantifies the mismatch at the boundary. Iterative methods, such as the Newton–Raphson algorithm in the single shooting case, or gradient-based optimisation techniques in the multi-shooting variant, are then used to adjust the initial guess. Both approaches require computing the sensitivity of the error function with respect to the initial guess, which can be elegantly obtained through an auxiliary (variational) system.

2 Initial Value Problems

Many models of real world systems can be formulated into initial value problems (IVPs). They arise when the starting conditions of a system are known and we are interested in the progression

of the system. In addition, the majority of well posed physical models that can be represented as IVPs give rise to a unique solution. This enhances the usefulness of finding numerical solutions to these systems as we have more confidence that further iterations of our method will lead to a numerical solution that converges to a 'true solution'.

As a reminder, an n^{th} order ODE system with initial conditions can be written as a vector first order system:

$$\frac{d\mathbf{Y}}{dx} = \mathbf{F}(x, \mathbf{Y}), \quad a \leq x \leq b,$$

where $\mathbf{Y} = (Y_1(x), \dots, Y_n(x))^T$ and $\mathbf{F} = (F_1(x, \mathbf{Y}), \dots, F_n(x, \mathbf{Y}))^T$, (1)

with initial data $\mathbf{Y}(a) = \boldsymbol{\alpha}$, $\boldsymbol{\alpha} = (\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_n)$.

The next step is then to define an iterative method by which to integrate forward. A simple method might be the 1st order Euler forward method. This iteration is defined as

$$x_i = a + ih,$$

$$\mathbf{Y}_{i+1} = \mathbf{Y}_i + h\mathbf{F}(x_i, \mathbf{Y}_i)$$

for $i = 0, \dots, \frac{b-a}{h} - 1$ where h is a constant step size.

A more advanced iteration method is that of the 4th order Runge-Kutta method defined as

$$x_i = a + ih,$$

$$\mathbf{k}_{i1} = \mathbf{F}(x_i, \mathbf{Y}_i), \quad \mathbf{k}_{i2} = \mathbf{F}\left(x_i + \frac{h}{2}, \mathbf{Y}_i + \frac{h}{2}\mathbf{k}_{i1}\right),$$

$$\mathbf{k}_{i3} = \mathbf{F}\left(x_i + \frac{h}{2}, \mathbf{Y}_i + \frac{h}{2}\mathbf{k}_{i2}\right), \quad \mathbf{k}_{i4} = \mathbf{F}(x_i + h, \mathbf{Y}_i + h\mathbf{k}_{i3}),$$

$$\mathbf{Y}_{i+1} = \mathbf{Y}_i + \frac{h}{6}(\mathbf{k}_{i1} + 2\mathbf{k}_{i2} + 2\mathbf{k}_{i3} + \mathbf{k}_{i4}),$$

for $i = 0, \dots, \frac{b-a}{h} - 1$ where h is a constant step size.

The codes for the Euler forward and 4th order Runge Kutta method are given in Appendix 6.1 and 6.2 respectively.

2.1 Validating code for the Euler forward and 4th order Runge Kutta method

In order to test our code we will use the following example:

$$\frac{d\mathbf{Y}}{dx} = \begin{pmatrix} x \\ Y_2 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \text{with } \mathbf{Y}(x=0) = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix}$$

on the interval $x \in [0, 1]$.

Note that the governing dynamics can be written as $\frac{dY_1}{dx} = x$ and $\frac{dY_2}{dx} = Y_2$. This is a decoupled system (no mixed dependence of Y_1 and Y_2) and so we can integrate each part separately. This leads to the general solutions: $Y_1 = \frac{x^2}{2} + A$ and $Y_2 = Be^x$ for some constants A and B . Plugging the general solutions into the initial conditions gives $A = 0$ and $B = 1$ leading to the unique solutions $Y_1 = \frac{x^2}{2}$ and $Y_2 = e^x$. This means that

Figure 1

$Y_1(x = 1) = 0.5$ and $Y_2(x = 1) = e$. Now that we have the analytical solutions we can compare the numerical solutions that each iterative method outputs and check that they are converging to the right solution and that they are converging at the rate that is expected. The derived class representing the system above is given in Appendix 6.3. Figure 1 shows that both numerical methods converge to the analytical solution of Y_2 at $x = 1$. In addition, both methods converge at their expected respective rates (Euler forward method is first order and 4th order Runge Kutta method 4th order). Both of these suggest that the algorithms are working as expected.

3 1 Dimensional Shooting Method

For the 1 dimensional shooting method for an n^{th} order ODE we have the exact same setup as in equation 1 but the initial data has the form

$$(Y_1(a), \dots, Y_{p-1}(a), Y_{p+1}(a), \dots, Y_n(a))^T = (\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_{p-1}, \alpha_{p+1}, \dots, \alpha_n)^T$$

and we have the additional boundary condition $Y_q(b) = \beta_q$ (2)

where $p, q \in \{1, \dots, n\}$.

Effectively, we have an initial condition, $Y_p(a)$ say, missing and instead have an additional boundary condition, $Y_q(b; g^*)$ say. The strategy would then be to guess the the unique value of the missing boundary condition, g^* say, that would result in the additional boundary condition, $Y_q(b)$. If we so happened to guess this g^* , we would be able to construct a numerical solution via an IVP iteration method. Unfortunately, it's unlikely we'll guess what g^* is first time; instead, we'll make a guess of the initial boundary condition, $Y_p(a) = g$ say. We would then evaluate the additional boundary condition with $Y_p(a) = g$ being used via an IVP iteration method, $Y_q(b; g)$ say, which would allow us to define a residual function, $\phi(g) = Y_q(b; g) - \beta_q$. All that remains is to find the g^* such that $\phi(g^*) = 0$. There a few ways to do this but we will employ the Newton Raphson method to find a root in order to update our guesses towards g^* . Remember, the Newton Raphson iteration method to find a root is given by $g_{i+1} = g_i - \frac{\phi'(g_i)}{\phi(g_i)}$ so the last part of the puzzle is determining $\phi'(g) = \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial g} = \frac{\partial Y_q(b; g)}{\partial g}$. You could use a primitive finite difference method but there is a subtle but brilliant alternative, an auxiliary system. This method involves defining the auxiliary system $Z_n = \frac{\partial Y_n(x; g)}{\partial g}$. Note that for $i \in \{1, \dots, n-1\}$, $\frac{\partial Z_i}{\partial x} = \frac{\partial^2 Y_i(x; g)}{\partial x \partial g} = \frac{\partial Y_{i+1}(x; g)}{\partial g} = Z_{i+1}$, $\frac{\partial Y_p(a; g)}{\partial g} = \frac{\partial g}{\partial g} = 1$ and for $j \in \{1, \dots, p-1, p+1, \dots, n\}$, $\frac{\partial Y_j(a; g)}{\partial g} = \frac{\partial \alpha_j}{\partial g} = 0$. This means the new Auxiliary system can be defined as

$$\frac{d\mathbf{Z}}{dx} = \mathbf{G}(x, \mathbf{Y}, \mathbf{Z}), \quad a \leq x \leq b,$$

where $\mathbf{Z} = (Z_1(x), \dots, Z_n(x))^T$ and $\mathbf{G} = (G_1(x, \mathbf{Y}, \mathbf{Z}), \dots, G_n(x, \mathbf{Y}, \mathbf{Z}))^T$, (3)

with initial data $\mathbf{Z}(a) = (0, \dots, 0, 1, 0, \dots, 0)$ where $Z_p(a) = 1$.

Here is where the key part happens, we can construct a numerical solution to the \mathbf{Z} system via an IVP iteration method which would allow us to evaluate $Z_q(b) = \frac{\partial Y_q(b; g)}{\partial g} = \phi'(g)$. Solving the main \mathbf{Y} system simultaneously with the Auxiliary \mathbf{Z} system allows you to compute $\phi'(g)$ for each g allowing you to update g towards g^* .

If we make the assumption that the n^{th} order ODE is linear and inhomogeneous then the ODE takes the form

$$c_{n+1}(x)Y_{n+1}(x; g) + \dots + c_1(x)Y_1(x; g) = b(x),$$

which means the Y_i system takes the form

$$\frac{d}{dx} \begin{pmatrix} Y_1 \\ \cdot \\ \cdot \\ \cdot \\ Y_{n-1} \\ Y_n \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} Y_2 \\ \cdot \\ \cdot \\ \cdot \\ Y_n \\ \frac{c_n(x)Y_n + \dots + c_1(x)Y_1 - b(x)}{-c_{n+1}(x)} \end{pmatrix}.$$

The Z_i system then takes the form

$$\frac{d}{dx} \begin{pmatrix} Z_1 \\ \cdot \\ \cdot \\ Z_{n-1} \\ Z_n \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} Z_2 \\ \cdot \\ \cdot \\ Z_n \\ \frac{c_n(x)Z_n + \dots + c_1(x)Z_1}{-c_{n+1}(x)} \end{pmatrix}$$

which is almost identical to the main system bar a change in notation. Examining the auxiliary system carefully we note that there is no Y_i dependence in any of the terms so this system decouples from the main system and can be solved separately. This means the output of the system is independent of our initial guess, g . Hence, $Z_q(b) = \phi'(g)$ will be the same regardless of g . The interpretation of this is that $\phi(g)$ is linear. Importantly, the Newton Raphson method will converge in exactly 1 step for a linear function (barring any roundoff error). This means we would only need to run the whole system once to find the correct parameter g^* . The main system would find $\phi(g)$ and the Auxiliary system would find $\phi'(g)$. It should be intuitive that the linear homogeneous case is effectively the same. The consequences of this is that the shooting method paired with the auxiliary system method is very effective in computing a numerical solution to linear BVPs.

If we extended the conditions to a non-linear ODE then the coefficients of the derivatives, $c_i(x)$, become functions of \mathbf{Y} , $c_i(x, \mathbf{Y})$. This doesn't change the $\frac{dZ_i}{dx}$ terms for $i \in \{1, \dots, n-1\}$ but it does for $i = n$. Namely,

$$\frac{dZ_n}{dx} = \frac{\partial^2 Y_n}{\partial x \partial g} = \frac{\partial}{\partial g} \left(\frac{c_n(x, \mathbf{Y})Z_n + \dots + c_1(x, \mathbf{Y})Z_1 - b(x, \mathbf{Y})}{-c_{n+1}(x, \mathbf{Y})} \right)$$

which will have terms of the form $\frac{\partial}{\partial g}(c_i(x, \mathbf{Y})Y_i) = c_i(x, \mathbf{Y})Z_i + \frac{\partial}{\partial g}(c_i(x, \mathbf{Y}))Y_i$ by the product rule which is a function of Y_i for non linear coefficient $c_i(x, \mathbf{Y})$. This means the Auxiliary system is no longer independent of \mathbf{Y} and by extension the initial guess g . This means the 2 systems need to be solved simultaneously and a new $\phi'(g)$ be found each time to update the guess. This can be done by defining a new variable $\mathbf{V} = (V_1, \dots, V_{2n}) = (Y_1, \dots, Y_n, Z_1, \dots, Z_n)$. The following subsection will explore such a non linear example.

3.1 Falkner Skan System

The falkner skan equation describes the flow of a fluid over a wedge. The equation is also mathematically representative of a flow within a pressure gradient (although the interpretation of the equation would then be different). The falkner skan equation is a generalisation of Blasius flow and Hemnitz flow which provide baseline models for fluid flows against surfaces.

The falkner skan equation is derived from the Navier Stokes equation. After a few well chosen assumptions about the flow, the PDE can be condensed into a 3rd order nonlinear homogeneous ODE given by

$$\begin{aligned} f'''(\eta) + f(\eta)f''(\eta) + \beta(1 - (f'(\eta))^2) &= 0 \\ f(0) = f'(0) &= 0 \\ f'(\eta) &\rightarrow 1 \text{ as } \eta \rightarrow \infty \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where f and η are representative of the flow and β is a function of the wedge angle or pressure gradient

Figure 2

depending on the context. Once the solution to f is numerically constructed via the shooting method, for example, the velocity profile and streamlines can be reconstructed from f and η .

In order to remain consistent with our existing notation, we have relabelled the variable, namely $f = y$ and $\eta = x$. The falkner skan BVP has the exact form needed in order to use the 1D shooting method with the exception of the additional boundary condition. In order to tackle this we approximate ∞ by choosing a suitably large x_{max} and verifying a convergence towards 1 by prescribing a tolerance, ε say, and checking whether $|f'(x_{max}) - 1| < \varepsilon$. The derived Falkner Skan system as well as the parameter iteration via the raphson newton method is given in appendix 6.4 and 6.5 respectively. The ouputted guess that satisfies the system g^* against β is shown in the Figure 2.

3.1.1 Sources of Error and Parameter Analysis

There are a multitude of modelling assumptions used in formulating the Falkner Skan equation. These include that the flow is steady, incompressible and 2D; the effects of viscosity only apply in a thin layer around the wedge and that the free-stream velocity can be expressed as a power law. If these conditions aren't met in a specific scenario then the application of this equation in that scenario is put into question.

Another problem comes in the form of the convergence of the Newton Raphson method. The Newton Raphson method will only converge is the initial guess is close enough to the root. This problem is amplified when the numerical solution is particularly sensitive to the guess as is the case in stiff systems like the one with large β (discussed later) . This begs the question: what is a good initial guess? One way of overcoming this problem is to apply parameter continuation. Namely, if we have an initial guess that converges for β , use the converged guess as the initial guess for $\beta + \Delta\beta$. You can also lower the tolerance and x_{max} conditions and get a converged guess in that system before using the converged guess as an initial guess on a tightened system.

The first source of numerical error that we will discuss comes from the use of x_{max} to approximate ∞ . The Falkner Skan, as described in equation 4, has a unique solution, $f(\eta)$, and by extension a unique value of the missing parameter, g^* . However, using different guesses leads to different trajectories of $f(\eta)$ and $f'(\eta)$ which leads to the possibility that these different trajectories could cross over for some value of $f'(\eta)$. More specifically, for a given x_{max} , you run the risk that there exists a g_1 and g_2 where $f'(x_{max}, g_1) = f'(x_{max}, g_2) = 1$ where $g_1 \neq g_2$. The consequence of this is that there will be multiple roots of $\phi(g)$ which means the guess the Newton Raphson method will converge to is dependent on the initial guess. It also begs the question which of these roots is correct? Thankfully, using a larger x_{max} reduces the chance of this happening for drastically different guesses as the different trajectories begin to diverge. However, when this turning point happens isn't initially clear. Having multiple solutions will be picked up by the shotting method if you make different guesses but this, generally speaking, is more of a problem for Boundary Value problems.

Another problem with using a x_{max} that is too small is that you run the risk that $f'(x_{max}, g^*)$ isn't within the given tolerance yet. Instead, you will pick up a guess that is within the tolerance but has got there too soon and will later leave it again. If $g > g^*$ the solution will grow too fast and enter the tolerance region too soon; this means if you have set x_{max} too small, you run the risk that the guess your programme outputted is too large.

The accumulation of roundoff error is given by $R\epsilon * \#steps = R\epsilon \frac{x_{max}}{h}$ where h is the stepsize, ϵ is the relative round off error (for double variables in C++ this is $\approx 10^{-16}$) and R is the number of operations within each step of an IVP iterator that can lead to a roundoff error. The truncation error for the 4th order Runge Kutta method is $K^* \# steps * h^5 = Kx_{max}h^4$ where K is a constant. This means the total error in the numerical method is given by

$$\text{Total Error} = Kx_{max}h^4 + R\epsilon \frac{x_{max}}{h} = x_{max} \left(Kh^4 + \frac{R\epsilon}{h} \right). \quad (5)$$

We can see that for large h , the truncation error dominates whilst for small h the roundoff error will dominate. One important difference between the 2 sources of error is that roundoff error is independent of any related operations whilst truncation error isn't. Another way of thinking about this is that if you were examining the numerical error of a solution under a perturbation of a parameter, it would be a smooth curve whilst the roundoff error would have a lot of noise. This helps in identifying which error is dominating. In the case of examining the error in $f'(x_{max})$, the relative error is equal to the absolute error.

Figure 3

In theory, we should get a unique solution for every well posed β but it is still important to see how each parameter effects our method so we can understand what role it plays in the governing system. We have already discussed why the choice of step size and x_{max} is important, especially for small x_{max} . Choosing a large x_{max} comes with a computational cost. Additionally, examining equation 5, we can see that $Kh^4 + \frac{R\epsilon}{h}$ will have a minimal value. This means that for a given tolerance of the total error, there will be an upper threshold of x_{max} that can be used such that the use g^* would stay within this tolerance by x_{max} . Figure 3(b) also demonstrates the effect of x_{max} on $\phi(g)$. As best seen in the case where $\beta = \frac{1}{3}$, the greater x_{max} , the steeper $\phi(g)$ becomes, the more the different trajectories diverge. This can also be seen very clearly in Figure 3(a), especially the cases where $\beta = \frac{1}{3}$ or $\beta = \frac{10}{11}$.

The effect of β is extensive both on the solution and the sensitivity on the construction of the solution. Figure 3(a) shows that with the correct guess, the rate at which the system converges (settles) is faster for a greater β . Alternatively, for a higher β , the system is more sensitive to

the guess used as we can see the solutions using underestimates or overestimates diverge much faster for larger β . Since these alternative trajectories diverge faster, another way of framing this is that the residual function is going to be more sensitive to x_{max} for larger β which can be seen in Figure 3(b). Furthermore, looking at Figure 3(b), the case where $\beta = \frac{10}{11}$ has a lot more noise in the error compared to the other two cases, this suggests that there is a link between larger β and dominating roundoff error which becomes worse for a larger x_{max} . The explanation of this comes from a closer look at equation 4. We know that for g^* , $f'(\eta) \rightarrow 1$ as $\eta \rightarrow \infty$. But if $f'(\eta) \approx 1$ then the effect of the roundoff error when computing $1 - (f'(\eta))^2$ is magnified. This error can lead to catastrophic cancellation when the errors accumulate. The role of β is that it will exaggerate the roundoff error through the $\beta(1 - (f'(\eta))^2)$ term. Since $f'(\eta) \rightarrow 1$ as $\eta \rightarrow \infty$, using a larger x_{max} means that $f'(x_{max})$ will be closer to 1 and so the effect of the roundoff error incurred by computing $1 - (f'(\eta))^2$ will be increased.

4 Multiple Dimension Shooting Method

The setup for the multi dimensional shooting method is much like that of the 1 dimensional case as described in system (2). The only difference is that instead of a single additional boundary condition we have multiple. These boundary conditions can be written as $Y_{q_i}(a_i) = \beta_i$ for $i = 1, \dots, m$ where $m \in \{1, \dots, n-1\}$, $a < a_1 \leq \dots \leq a_m = b$ and $q_1, \dots, q_m \in \{1, \dots, n\}$. Note that similar to the 1 dimensional case, these boundary conditions need to be well posed. We can then express the m remaining initial condition guesses as $Y_{p_i}(a) = g_i$ for $i = 1, \dots, m$ where p_i represent the indices of \mathbf{Y} where there is an initial condition missing. The last thing is to define the error at each of the additional boundary conditions, $\phi_i(\mathbf{g}) = Y_{q_i}(a_i; \mathbf{g}) - \beta_i$ for $i = 1, \dots, m$ where $\mathbf{g} = (g_1, \dots, g_m)^T$.

It would be tempting to define a combined residual function as $\phi(\mathbf{g}) = \phi_1(\mathbf{g}) + \dots + \phi_m(\mathbf{g})$ but this would be ignorant of the the fact that the individual residuals can be negative or positive which would lead to cancellation. Another plausible possibility would be $\phi(\mathbf{g}) = |\phi_1(\mathbf{g})| + \dots + |\phi_m(\mathbf{g})|$ however a more typical approach is to use the squares, $\phi(\mathbf{g}) = \phi_1^2(\mathbf{g}) + \dots + \phi_m^2(\mathbf{g})$.

The task is then to find the guesses such that $\phi(\mathbf{g}) = 0$. Whilst this looks like a root finding problem as in the 1 dimensional case, it can also be viewed as a minimisation problem as $\phi(\mathbf{g}) \geq 0$. A valid approach would then be to iterate towards better guesses via gradient descent. This iteration is defined as

$$\mathbf{g}_{i+1} = \mathbf{g}_i - \eta \nabla \phi(\mathbf{g}) = \mathbf{g}_i - \eta \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\partial \phi(\mathbf{g})}{\partial g_1} \\ \cdot \\ \cdot \\ \cdot \\ \frac{\partial \phi(\mathbf{g})}{\partial g_m} \end{pmatrix}$$

where η is a prescribed learning rate. Note that for $i = 1, \dots, m$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \phi(\mathbf{g})}{\partial g_i} &= \frac{\partial(\phi_1^2(\mathbf{g}) + \dots + \phi_m^2(\mathbf{g}))}{\partial g_i} = \frac{\partial(\phi_1^2(\mathbf{g}))}{\partial g_i} + \dots + \frac{\partial(\phi_m^2(\mathbf{g}))}{\partial g_i} \\ &= \frac{\partial(\phi_1^2(\mathbf{g}))}{\partial \phi_1(\mathbf{g})} \frac{\partial \phi_1(\mathbf{g})}{\partial g_i} + \dots + \frac{\partial(\phi_m^2(\mathbf{g}))}{\partial \phi_m(\mathbf{g})} \frac{\partial \phi_m(\mathbf{g})}{\partial g_i} = 2\phi_1(\mathbf{g}) \frac{\partial \phi_1(\mathbf{g})}{\partial g_i} + \dots + 2\phi_m(\mathbf{g}) \frac{\partial \phi_m(\mathbf{g})}{\partial g_i} \\ &= 2\phi_1(\mathbf{g}) \frac{\partial(Y_{q_1}(a_1; \mathbf{g}) - \beta_1)}{\partial g_i} + \dots + 2\phi_m(\mathbf{g}) \frac{\partial(Y_{q_m}(a_m; \mathbf{g}) - \beta_m)}{\partial g_i} = 2\phi_1(\mathbf{g}) \frac{\partial(Y_{q_1}(a_1; \mathbf{g}))}{\partial g_i} + \dots + 2\phi_m(\mathbf{g}) \frac{\partial(Y_{q_m}(a_m; \mathbf{g}))}{\partial g_i}. \end{aligned}$$

We can then define the Auxiliary systems $Z_{i,j} = \frac{\partial Y_j(x_i; \mathbf{g})}{\partial g_i}$ for $i = 1, \dots, m$ and $j = 1, \dots, n$. This

\mathbf{Z}_i system behaves very similarly to that of the 1 dimensional system, namely

$$\frac{d\mathbf{Z}_i}{dx} = \mathbf{G}(z, \mathbf{Y}, \mathbf{Z}_i), \quad \begin{pmatrix} Z_{i,1}(a) \\ \vdots \\ Z_{i,p_i-1}(a) \\ Z_{i,p_i}(a) \\ Z_{i,p_i+1}(a) \\ \vdots \\ Z_{i,n}(a) \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ \vdots \\ 0 \\ 1 \\ 0 \\ \vdots \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (6)$$

We can then use an IVP iterative method (simultaneously with the \mathbf{Y} system if the original ODE is non-linear) to evaluate $Z_{i,q_j}(a_j) = \frac{\partial(Y_{q_j}(a_j; \mathbf{g}))}{\partial g_i}$ for $i, j = 1, \dots, m$. This gives us the exact derivatives that we need to update g_i via the gradient descent method. More specifically, an updated g_i is given by,

$$g_i - 2\eta[\phi_1(\mathbf{g})Z_{i,q_1}(a_1) + \dots + \phi_m(\mathbf{g})Z_{i,q_m}(a_m)].$$

To be more succinct, we can define the m dimensional vector $\phi(\mathbf{g}) = (\phi_1(\mathbf{g}), \dots, \phi_m(\mathbf{g}))^T$ and the $m \times m$ dimensional matrix $\mathbf{Z}_{i,j}(\mathbf{g}) = Z_{i,q_j}(a_j)$ then

$$\mathbf{g}_{i+1} = \mathbf{g}_i - \eta \mathbf{Z}_{i,j}(\mathbf{g}_i) \phi(\mathbf{g}_i)$$

where η here has absorbed the factor of 2. If we have a n^{th} order nonlinear ODE with m additional boundary conditions then we have to use an IVP iterative method over a $n(m+1)$ dimensional vector. Note that we could potentially evaluate $\mathbf{Z}_{i,j}(\mathbf{g})$ in one pass but this would require our step size to be adjusted so that the iteration covers $x = a_1, \dots, a_j$. Alternatively, one could approximate the $\mathbf{Z}_{i,j}(\mathbf{g})$ with a value of x close to a_j . If m is small, you could also carry out the IVP iteration m times setting a_j as the different end points each time. The choice of the learning rate, η , is very important in increasing the chance that the iterations converge. The theory of gradient descent has been heavily studied with the rapid advancement of neural networks. Following the given explanation is a bit of a notation following task so we have provided an example to follow.

4.1 An Example

Consider the linear homogeneous ODE system

$$y'''(x) = 0, \quad (7)$$

with conditions $y(0) = 1, \quad y(\frac{1}{2}) = 0, \quad y(1) = 2.$

In order to verify our numerical method works we can find the analytical solution of this simple system:

$$\begin{aligned} y'''(x) = 0 &\implies y''(x) = A_1 \implies y'(x) = A_1x + B \\ &\implies y(x) = \frac{A_1}{2}x^2 + Bx + C = Ax^2 + Bx + C \end{aligned}$$

where A, B, C are unknown constants and $A_1 = 2A$. Then, using the conditions we have that $y(0) = 1 \implies C = 1$ as well as $y(\frac{1}{2}) = 0 \implies \frac{A}{4} + \frac{B}{2} + 1 = 0$ and $y(1) = 2 \implies A + B + 1 = 2$. Solving this system simultaneously gives $A = 6$ and $B = -5$ leaving us with $y(x) = 6x^2 - 5x + 1$.

Figure 4

Using the notation above, we will then use an IVP iteration method to solve

$$\frac{d}{dx} \begin{pmatrix} V_1 \\ V_2 \\ V_3 \\ V_4 \\ V_5 \\ V_6 \\ V_7 \\ V_8 \\ V_9 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} V_2 \\ V_3 \\ 0 \\ V_5 \\ V_6 \\ 0 \\ V_8 \\ V_9 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \begin{pmatrix} V_1(0) \\ V_2(0) \\ V_3(0) \\ V_4(0) \\ V_5(0) \\ V_6(0) \\ V_7(0) \\ V_8(0) \\ V_9(0) \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ g_1 \\ g_2 \\ 0 \\ 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix}.$$

The update of \mathbf{g} will be governed by:

$$\mathbf{g}_{i+1} = \mathbf{g}_i - \eta \begin{pmatrix} V_4(\frac{1}{2}; \mathbf{g}_i) & V_4(1; \mathbf{g}_i) \\ V_7(\frac{1}{2}; \mathbf{g}_i) & V_7(1; \mathbf{g}_i) \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \phi_1(\mathbf{g}_i) \\ \phi_2(\mathbf{g}_i) \end{pmatrix}.$$

Figure 4 shows how the numerical solution approaches the analytical solution with increasing iterations of \mathbf{g} . The code for this is given in Appendix 6.6 and 6.7.

5 Conclusion

(The header file as well as the entirety of my code is contained within Appendix 6.8 and 6.9 respectively). The shooting method is a highly effective numerical approach for solving higher-order ODEs formulated as BVPs. By transforming the BVP into an IVP and iteratively refining the initial conditions, it leverages well-established IVP solvers to tackle otherwise challenging problems. When combined with auxiliary systems and iterative techniques such as the Newton–Raphson or gradient descent methods, the shooting method becomes particularly powerful. For linear ODEs, convergence is typically achieved in a single iteration (up to round-off errors). For nonlinear ODEs, integrating both the main system and auxiliary system simultaneously enables effective updates to the initial guess in each iteration.

In practice, enhancements such as parameter continuation can significantly improve the robustness of the shooting method. For example, starting with a system of reduced stiffness and gradually increasing the stiffness parameter can help generate an initial guess that is more likely to converge for the original problem. Similarly, relaxing and then tightening the tolerance of the residual function can guide the solution toward the correct boundary conditions.

However, the shooting method does face challenges when applied to stiff problems, as it inherits—and often amplifies—the stability issues typical of explicit IVP solvers. Although parameter continuation provides a workaround, it can be computationally expensive, particularly when continuation must be performed across multiple parameters. Furthermore, the method still depends on having at least one initial guess that converges, which is not always easy to obtain. Unlike other numerical methods used to solve ODEs formulated as BVPs, the shooting method isn’t easily extendable to solve PDEs.

These drawbacks do not imply that the shooting method should be abandoned for stiff problems. Instead, it can be enhanced by incorporating implicit IVP solvers (such as implicit Euler) or adaptive multistep schemes within the shooting framework. Implicit solvers naturally damp out the fast-decaying components responsible for stiffness, while adaptive multistep methods adjust step sizes to balance accuracy and efficiency. Using these advanced solvers within the shooting iteration allows the method to retain its simplicity while extending its applicability to a broader class of problems.

In summary, the shooting method remains an elegant and versatile tool for solving BVPs. With careful implementation—especially through the use of implicit and adaptive techniques—it can effectively handle even stiff or highly sensitive systems while maintaining its core advantages.

6 Appendix

6.1

```
1 int EulerSolve(int steps, double a, double b, MVector &Y, MFunction &F)
2 {
3     std::ofstream demofile;
4     demofile.open("Euler_ODE_solve");
5     if (!demofile) return 1;
6     double h=(b-a)/steps;
7     if (b<a) return 1;
8     demofile<<a<<" , "<<Y<<"\n";
9     for(int i=0; i<steps;i++)
10    {
11        Y=Y+h*F(a,Y);
12        a+=h;
13        demofile<<a<<" , "<<Y<<"\n";
14    }
15    demofile.close();
16    return 0;
17 }
```

6.2

```
18 int RungeKuttaSolve(int steps, double a, double b, MVector &Y, MFunction &F)
19 {
20     std::ofstream demofile;
21     demofile.open("Runge_Kutta_ODE_solve");
22     if (!demofile) return 1;
23     MVector k1 ,k2, k3, k4;
24     double h=(b-a)/steps;
25     if (b<a) return 1;
26     demofile<<a<<" , "<<Y<<"\n";
27     for(int i=0; i<steps;i++)
28     {
29         k1=F(a,Y);
30         k2=F(a+(h/2),Y+(h/2)*k1);
31         k3=F(a+(h/2),Y+(h/2)*k2);
32         k4=F(a+h,Y+h*k3);
33         Y=Y+(h/6)*(k1+2*k2+2*k3+k4);
34         a+=h;
35         demofile<<a<<" , "<<Y<<"\n";
36         std::cout<<Y[0]<<std::endl;
37     }
38     demofile.close();
39     return 0;
40 }
```

6.3

```
41 //derived class F2
42 class FunctionF2 : public MFunction
43 {
44     public:
45         virtual MVector operator()(const double& x, const MVector& y)
46         {
47             MVector temp(2);
48             temp[0] = x;
```

```

49     temp[1] =y[1];
50     return temp;
51     }
52 };

```

6.4

```

53 // derived Falkner Skan class
54 class FalknerSkan : public MFunction
55 {
56     public:
57         // constructor to initialise kappa
58         FalknerSkan() {beta=0.0;}
59         MVector operator()(const double& x,const MVector& y)
60         {
61             MVector temp(6);
62             temp[0] = y[1];
63             temp[1] = y[2];
64             temp[2] = beta*(y[1]*y[1]-1)-y[0]*y[2];
65             temp[3] = y[4];
66             temp[4] = y[5];
67             temp[5] = 2*beta*y[1]*y[4]-y[2]*y[3]-y[0]*y[5];
68             return temp;
69         }
70         void SetBeta(double b) {beta=b;} // change kappa
71     private:
72         double beta; // class member variable, accessible within
73         // all Eqnip5Derivs member functions
74 };

```

6.5

```

75 MVector FalknerSkanGuessr(double beta, double guess, int end, int maxNewtonSteps)
76 {
77     FalknerSkan f;
78     f.SetBeta(beta);
79     MVector y;
80     int maxnumintstep=end*100;
81     double tol=1e-8, phi;
82     for (int i=0; i<maxNewtonSteps;i++)
83     {
84         y={0,0,guess,0,0,1};
85         RungeKuttaSolve(maxnumintstep,0,end,y,f);
86         phi=y[1]-1;
87         double phidash=y[4];
88         if (std::abs(phi)<tol) break;
89         guess -= phi/phidash;
90     }
91     MVector v={beta,guess};
92     return v;
93 }

```

6.6

```

94 // derived quadratic tester class
95 class quadratictester : public MFunction

```

```

96 {
97     public:
98         MVector operator()(const double& x, const MVector& y)
99         {
100             MVector temp(9);
101             temp[0] = y[1];
102             temp[1] = y[2];
103             temp[2] = 0;
104             temp[3] = y[4];
105             temp[4] = y[5];
106             temp[5] = 0;
107             temp[6] = y[7];
108             temp[7] = y[8];
109             temp[8] = 0;
110             return temp;
111         }
112 };

```

6.7

```

113 MVector quadraticguesser(double guessp, double guessq, int descentSteps, double nu, double
    tol)
114 {
115     quadratictester f;
116     MVector y;
117     double phi=1.0, phi1, phi2, phi1p, phi1q, phi2p, phi2q;
118     double j=0;
119     for(int i=0; i<descentSteps; i++)
120     {
121         phi=0.0;
122         y={1, guessp, guessq, 0, 1, 0, 0, 0, 1};
123         RungeKuttaSolve(0.5*100, 0, 0.5, y, f);
124         phi1=y[0];
125         phi+=phi1*phi1;
126         phi1p=y[3];
127         phi1q=y[6];
128         y={1, guessp, guessq, 0, 1, 0, 0, 0, 1};
129         RungeKuttaSolve(100, 0, 1, y, f);
130         phi2=(y[0]-2);
131         phi+=phi2*phi2;
132         phi2p=y[3];
133         phi2q=y[6];
134         if (std::abs(phi)<tol) break;
135         guessp-=nu*2*(phi1*phi1p+phi2*phi2p);
136         guessq-=nu*2*(phi1*phi1q+phi2*phi2q);
137         j++;
138     }
139     MVector V={guessp, guessq, phi, j};
140     return V;
141 }

```

6.8

```

142 #ifndef MVECTOR_H // the 'include guard'
143 #define MVECTOR_H // see C++ Primer Sec. 2.9.2
144
145 #include <vector>
146 #include <iostream>

```

```

147
148 // Class that represents a mathematical vector
149 class MVector
150 {
151 public:
152     // constructors
153     MVector() {}
154     explicit MVector(int n) : v(n) {}
155     MVector(int n, double x) : v(n, x) {}
156     MVector(std::initializer_list<double> l) : v(l) {}
157
158     // access element (lvalue) (see example sheet 5, q5.6)
159     double &operator[](int index)
160     {
161         return v[index];
162     }
163
164     // access element (rvalue) (see example sheet 5, q5.7)
165     double operator[](int index) const {
166         return v[index];
167     }
168
169     int size() const { return v.size(); } // number of elements
170
171 private:
172     std::vector<double> v;
173 };
174
175 //1.2.1
176
177 inline MVector operator*(const double& lhs, const MVector& rhs)
178 {
179     MVector temp = rhs;
180     for (int i=0; i<temp.size(); i++) temp[i]*=lhs;
181     return temp;
182 }
183
184 inline MVector operator*(const MVector& rhs, const double& lhs)
185 {
186     MVector temp = rhs;
187     for (int i=0; i<temp.size(); i++) temp[i]*=lhs;
188     return temp;
189 }
190
191 inline MVector operator/(const MVector& rhs, const double& lhs)
192 {
193     MVector temp = rhs;
194     for (int i=0; i<temp.size(); i++) temp[i]/=lhs;
195     return temp;
196 }
197
198 inline MVector operator+(const MVector& lhs, const MVector& rhs)
199 {
200     MVector temp = rhs;
201     for (int i=0; i<temp.size(); i++) temp[i]=lhs[i]+rhs[i];
202     return temp;
203 }
204
205 inline MVector operator-(const MVector& lhs, const MVector& rhs)
206 {
207

```

```

208     MVector temp = rhs;
209     for (int i=0; i<temp.size(); i++) temp[i]=lhs[i]-rhs[i];
210     return temp;
211 }
212
213 std::ostream& operator<<(std::ostream& os, const MVector& v)
214 {
215     int n = v.size();
216     os << "<<v[0];
217     for(int i=1; i<n;i++) os<<","<<v[i];
218     os << ")";
219     return os;
220 }
221
222 #endif

```

6.9

```

223 #include <iostream>
224 #include "mvector.h"
225 #include <cmath>
226 #include <fstream>
227
228 //base class
229 class MFunction
230 {
231     public:
232     virtual MVector operator()(const double& x, const MVector& y) = 0;
233 };
234
235 //derived f1 class
236 class FunctionF1 : public MFunction
237 {
238     public:
239     virtual MVector operator()(const double& x, const MVector& y)
240     {
241         MVector temp(2);
242         temp[0] = y[0] + x*y[1];
243         temp[1] = x*y[0] - y[1];
244         return temp;
245     }
246 };
247
248 //derived class F2
249 class FunctionF2 : public MFunction
250 {
251     public:
252     virtual MVector operator()(const double& x, const MVector& y)
253     {
254         MVector temp(2);
255         temp[0] = x;
256         temp[1] =y[1];
257         return temp;
258     }
259 };
260
261 //derived class F3
262 class FunctionF3 : public MFunction
263 {
264     public:

```

```

265     virtual MVector operator()(const double& x, const MVector& y)
266     {
267     MVector temp(1);
268     temp[0] = 2*x;
269     return temp;
270     }
271 };
272
273 // derived eqnip5 class
274 class Eqnip5Derivs : public MFunction
275 {
276     public:
277     // constructor to initialise kappa
278     Eqnip5Derivs() {kappa=1.0;}
279     MVector operator()(const double& x,const MVector& y)
280     {
281     MVector temp(4);
282     temp[0] = y[1];
283     temp[1] = -kappa*y[1] - x*y[0];
284     temp[2] = y[3];
285     temp[3] = -kappa*y[3] - x*y[2];
286     return temp;
287     }
288     void SetKappa(double k) {kappa=k;} // change kappa
289     private:
290     double kappa; // class member variable, accessible within
291     // all Eqnip5Derivs member functions
292 };
293
294 // derived Falkner Skan class
295 class FalknerSkan : public MFunction
296 {
297     public:
298     // constructor to initialise kappa
299     FalknerSkan() {beta=0.0;}
300     MVector operator()(const double& x,const MVector& y)
301     {
302     MVector temp(6);
303     temp[0] = y[1];
304     temp[1] = y[2];
305     temp[2] = beta*(y[1]*y[1]-1)-y[0]*y[2];
306     temp[3] = y[4];
307     temp[4] = y[5];
308     temp[5] = 2*beta*y[1]*y[4]-y[2]*y[3]-y[0]*y[5];
309     return temp;
310     }
311     void SetBeta(double b) {beta=b;} // change kappa
312     private:
313     double beta; // class member variable, accessible within
314     // all Eqnip5Derivs member functions
315 };
316
317 // derived quadratic tester class
318 class quadratictester : public MFunction
319 {
320     public:
321     MVector operator()(const double& x,const MVector& y)
322     {
323     MVector temp(9);
324     temp[0] = y[1];
325     temp[1] = y[2];

```

```

326     temp[2] = 0;
327     temp[3] = y[4];
328     temp[4] = y[5];
329     temp[5] = 0;
330     temp[6] = y[7];
331     temp[7] = y[8];
332     temp[8] = 0;
333     return temp;
334 }
335 };
336
337
338
339
340 // Declaration for an Euler scheme ODE solver
341 int EulerSolve(int steps, double a, double b, MVector &Y, MFunction &F)
342 {
343     std::ofstream demofile;
344     demofile.open("Euler_ODE_solve");
345     if (!demofile) return 1;
346     double h=(b-a)/steps;
347     if (b<a) return 1;
348     demofile<<a<<" , "<<Y<<"\n";
349     for(int i=0; i<steps;i++)
350     {
351         Y=Y+h*F(a,Y);
352         a+=h;
353         demofile<<a<<" , "<<Y<<"\n";
354     }
355     demofile.close();
356     return 0;
357 }
358
359
360 // Runge Kutta Solver
361 int RungeKuttaSolve(int steps, double a, double b, MVector &Y, MFunction &F)
362 {
363     std::ofstream demofile;
364     demofile.open("Runge_Kutta_ODE_solve");
365     if (!demofile) return 1;
366     MVector k1 ,k2, k3, k4;
367     double h=(b-a)/steps;
368     if (b<a) return 1;
369     demofile<<a<<" , "<<Y<<"\n";
370     for(int i=0; i<steps;i++)
371     {
372         k1=F(a,Y);
373         k2=F(a+(h/2),Y+(h/2)*k1);
374         k3=F(a+(h/2),Y+(h/2)*k2);
375         k4=F(a+h,Y+h*k3);
376         Y=Y+(h/6)*(k1+2*k2+2*k3+k4);
377         a+=h;
378         demofile<<a<<" , "<<Y<<"\n";
379         std::cout<<Y[0]<<std::endl;
380     }
381     demofile.close();
382     return 0;
383 }
384
385 MVector FalknerSkanGuessr(double beta, double guess, int end, int maxNewtonSteps)
386 {

```

```

387     FalknerSkan f;
388     f.SetBeta(beta);
389     MVector y;
390     int maxnumintstep=end*100;
391     double tol=1e-8, phi;
392     for (int i=0; i<maxNewtonSteps;i++)
393     {
394         y={0,0,guess,0,0,1};
395         RungeKuttaSolve(maxnumintstep,0,end,y,f);
396         phi=y[1]-1;
397         double phidash=y[4];
398         if (std::abs(phi)<tol) break;
399         guess -= phi/phidash;
400     }
401     MVector v={beta,guess};
402     return v;
403 }
404
405 MVector quadraticguesser(double guessp, double guessq, int descentSteps, double nu, double
    tol)
406 {
407     quadratictester f;
408     MVector y;
409     double phi=1.0, phi1, phi2, phi1p, phi1q, phi2p, phi2q;
410     double j=0;
411     for(int i=0;i<descentSteps;i++)
412     {
413         phi=0.0;
414         y={1,guessp,guessq,0,1,0,0,0,1};
415         RungeKuttaSolve(0.5*100,0,0.5,y,f);
416         phi1=y[0];
417         phi+=phi1*phi1;
418         phi1p=y[3];
419         phi1q=y[6];
420         y={1,guessp,guessq,0,1,0,0,0,1};
421         RungeKuttaSolve(100,0,1,y,f);
422         phi2=(y[0]-2);
423         phi+=phi2*phi2;
424         phi2p=y[3];
425         phi2q=y[6];
426         if (std::abs(phi)<tol) break;
427         guessp-=nu*2*(phi1*phi1p+phi2*phi2p);
428         guessq-=nu*2*(phi1*phi1q+phi2*phi2q);
429         j++;
430     }
431     MVector V={guessp,guessq,phi,j};
432     return V;
433 }
434
435 int main()
436 { /*report q1
437     {
438         FunctionF2 f;
439         MVector y={0,1};
440         EulerSolve(100,0,1,y,f);
441         y={0,1};
442         RungeKuttaSolve(100,0,1,y,f);
443         std::cout<<FalknerSkanGuesser(0.1, 0.4, 5, 5)<<std::endl;
444     }
445     */
446     /*report q2

```

```

447 {
448     FunctionF2 f;
449     MVector y={0,1};
450     for(int i=1;i<=100;i++)
451     {
452         RungeKuttaSolve(i,0,1,y,f);
453         std::cout.precision(12);
454         std::cout<<y[1]<<std::endl;
455         y={0,1};
456     }
457 }
458 */
459 /* later
460 {
461     double g=0.47, beta=0;
462     double h=1/100.0;
463
464     MVector VIn={5,10,15,20,25,30,50,75,100,125,150,160,170,180,190,200};
465     for(int i=0;i<=100;i++)
466     {
467         for(int j=0;j<VIn.size();j++)
468         {
469             g=FalknerSkanGuessr(beta,g,VIn[j],10)[1];
470         }
471         if (g>10) break;
472         std::cout.precision(18);
473         std::cout<< FalknerSkanGuessr(beta,g,200,5)[1]<<std::endl;
474         beta+=h;
475     }
476 }
477 */
478 /*residuals
479 {
480     FalknerSkan f;
481     f.SetBeta(10.0/11.0);
482     MVector y;
483     int end=20;
484     int maxnumintstep=end*100;
485     double guess=1;
486     double h=0.001;
487     for ( int i=0; i<=500;i++)
488     {
489         y={0,0,guess,0,0,1};
490         RungeKuttaSolve(maxnumintstep,0,end,y,f);
491         if(std::abs(y[1]-1)<100)
492         {
493             std::cout<<y[1]-1<<std::endl;
494         }
495         guess+=h;
496     }
497 }
498 */
499 /*f''
500 {
501     double guess0=0.4695999884;
502     double guessthird=0.8021255928;
503     double guesselevth=1.182817236074818;
504     FalknerSkan f;
505     f.SetBeta(1.0/3.0);
506     MVector y={0,0,guessthird+0.25*guessthird,0,0,1};
507     int end=5;

```

```

508     int maxnumintstep=end*100;
509     RungeKuttaSolve(maxnumintstep,0,end,y,f);
510 }
511 */
512 /*extra
513 {
514     quadratictester f;
515     MVector y;
516     double phi=0.0, phi1, phi2, phi1p, phi1q, phi2p, phi2q, end1=0.5, end2=1.0, guessp
           =1, guessq=2, nu=0.01;
517     y={1,guessp,guessq,0,1,0,0,0,1};
518     RungeKuttaSolve(end1*100,0,end1,y,f);
519     phi1=y[0];
520     phi+=phi1*phi1;
521     phi1p=y[3];
522     phi1q=y[6];
523     y={1,guessp,guessq,0,1,0,0,0,1};
524     RungeKuttaSolve(end2*100,0,end2,y,f);
525     phi2=(y[0]-2);
526     phi+=phi2*phi2;
527     phi2p=y[3];
528     phi2q=y[6];
529     std::cout<<guessp<<" , "<<guessq<<" , "<<phi<<std::endl;
530     guessp-=nu*2*(phi1*phi1p+phi2*phi2p);
531     guessq-=nu*2*(phi1*phi1q+phi2*phi2q);
532     phi=0;
533     y={1,guessp,guessq,0,1,0,0,0,1};
534     RungeKuttaSolve(end1*100,0,end1,y,f);
535     phi1=y[0];
536     phi+=phi1*phi1;
537     phi1p=y[3];
538     phi1q=y[6];
539     y={1,guessp,guessq,0,1,0,0,0,1};
540     RungeKuttaSolve(end2*100,0,end2,y,f);
541     phi2=(y[0]-2);
542     phi+=phi2*phi2;
543     phi2p=y[3];
544     phi2q=y[6];
545     std::cout<<guessp<<" , "<<guessq<<" , "<<phi<<std::endl;
546 }
547 }
548 1,3,7*/
549 {
550     //std::cout<<quadraticguesser(1,1,700,0.1,0.001)<<std::endl;
551     quadratictester f;
552     MVector y={1,-4.20448,10.2469,0,1,0,0,0,1};
553     RungeKuttaSolve(100,0,1,y,f);
554 }
555
556     return 0;
557 }

```
